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figure 1

The aim of this research

Central to this research is a design project entitled 'The Virtual Lunar Development Project'. The purpose of the research was to test the suitability of the KANSEI Parallel Designing method for the theme 'How can the demands of users be reflected in a design project?'. 15

Outline of the virtual lunar development project

This design project was carried out by 21 industrial design students of the Institute of Art & Design of the University of Tsukuba. In this project students had to propose designs for equipment and facilities needed for living on the moon. All the design proposals were published on the internet. It was possible for the general public to comment on these proposals so that the students could rework their designs based on these comments. The Virtual Lunar Development Project forms part of 'The Internet Symposium – to the moon again', jointly organized by the Harada Laboratory, the National Space Development Agency, and the Institute for Space and Astronautical Sciences. The web site can be found at <http://moon.nasda.go.jp>.

The contents of the project

The 21 students each chose one subject. They were as follows:

- Moon house
- Moon illumination
- Hot spring on the moon
- Amusement
- Space suit
- Transportation system
- Motorcycle
- Logistics system
- Farm system
- Space food
- Space hospital
- Space power plant
- Resource development
- Moon park
- Device of walking
- Space guard system
- Communication system
- Space station
- Portable rover
- Public transportation system
- Rover

The aim of the project

In this project it was explored how to respond to questions of the primary users of a product. How could the demands of users be incorporated in design? In this project students were taken to be the planners (hereinafter called planners) and the visitors of the website were taken to be the users (hereinafter called users). The proposals of the planners could be evaluated at any time by the users and the users' demands were considered in subsequent designs. Questions and advice were transmitted to the planners via email links on the WWW. The planners could refer to this information and take it into consideration in their redesigns. If the students could not answer a question, it was forwarded to the mailing lists of the National Space Development Agency, or the Institute of Space and Astronautical Sciences. Then the answers were provided by a professional space scientists. The network system is shown in figure 2.

Figure 3 shows the structure between the index page and the contents of each planner's work.

figure 2

The results of the project

The design work of the students, started on October 8, 1998, was evaluated on December 18, 1998. The website was accessed 1967 times and 230 messages were received in the period November till January. 45 e-mail questions were sent to the National Space Development Agency by the planners. We learned the importance of the advisory system through this task.

figure 3

Hypotheses

The author verified the following hypotheses from the point of view of how the designs of the planners were influenced through communication with the users under the circumstances described in previous chapters.

Hypothesis 1

The design process by planner is not a serial process, but it likens a parallel process, in which interactive messages are exchanged between planners and users.

Hypothesis 2

The image association of the users on the web site influences the planners' works. It also influences the evaluation of the planners' works.

Verification of hypothesis 1

Comparison of design processes

A presentation consists of nine elements (figure 4):

- | | | |
|------|----------------------|--|
| 01 | [title] | Concept plan using quantification model III analysis. |
| 02 | [image sketch] | Expression of image by computer graphics (CG) collage |
| 03 | [functional element] | Extraction of mechanism element. |
| 04 | [feature component] | Making of specification orthogonalization array table. |
| 05-1 | [idea sketch] | Idea sketch based on orthogonalization array table of specification |
| 05-2 | [evaluation] | Five score evaluation by WWW user |
| 06 | [modeling] | The model was made referring to the evaluation to the idea sketch. |
| 07 | [CG simulation] | CG animation by dynamic expression of modeling. |
| 08 | [adaptable solution] | Extraction of the best specified composition by conjoint measurement analysis. |
| 09 | [final proposal] | Consideration of analysis result. |

Discussion

The class renewed the presentation on the website every week, and accepted advice from visitors of the website. Figure 5 shows that not all planners begin with the general idea building in languages. This particular planner expresses the fragment of the image suddenly and has shown an animated proposal from the start. It can be said that the interaction between users and planners using the WWW made a variety of design processes possible.

Design is *KANSEI* oriented work, since it is not completely logical. This applies to the production process of the works of art such as a painting and sculpture as well. Nevertheless, conventional design edu-

figure 4

ation teaches a serial approach to the design process.

Verification of hypothesis 2

The verification by log analysis

User activities on the website of 'The Virtual Lunar Development Project' were recorded on the WWW server as log files. Through analysis of this log, the behaviour of the users becomes clear. The log contains data such as the visited page, the movement order between the pages, the time spent on a particular page and whether a message was sent. Part of the log files which the server actually produced are shown below:

```
[03/Nov/1998:05:01:24 +0900] GET /nasda/lunar/KAMIYA/kamiya.jpg HTTP/1.0 • E 200 0
[03/Nov/1998:05:01:24 +0900] GET /nasda/lunar/SUGIYAMA/sugi01.htm HTTP/1.0 • E200 3014
[03/Nov/1998:05:01:29 +0900] GET /nasda/lunar/SUGIYAMA/01.jpg HTTP/1.0 • E200 69214
[03/Nov/1998:05:01:33 +0900] GET /nasda/lunar/SUGIYAMA/sugi02.htm HTTP/1.0 • E200 3103
[03/Nov/1998:05:01:33 +0900] GET /nasda/lunar/NOHARA/nohara01.htm HTTP/1.0 • E200 2990
```


figure 6

figure 5

Analysis of the WWW log

The following process was used for analyzing the WWW log.

1. Transferring the log file to a spreadsheet in Microsoft Excel.
2. Extracting the access record of a particular WWW user.
3. Working out the browsing time for a specific document and compiling the outcome in a table.

The access to each page of planner "N" in January 1999 is shown in Figure 6.

The effect of messages from users on design

The author examined the correlation between the evaluation score of the planners' proposals and the access count of messages from users. During a meeting on December 18,

the proposals were rated on a five points scale by 9 experts consisting of members of staff from design faculties and scientists from NASDA.

The evaluative score was used as a standard variable. The following 5 items were used as explanatory variables.

1. Total message count to each planner.
2. Number of messages to the title page.
3. Number of messages to the concept page.
4. Number of messages to the preference page of sketches.
5. Number of messages to the final model page.

These categories are shown in Table 1. This was done to find what influenced the evaluation of the design proposals, either the number or messages or the kinds of pages which were accessed.

Result of the log analysis

Table 2 shows the results as obtained by analyzing the data through a Quantification Model I analysis. It should be noted, however, that the reliability of the forecasting count was not so high (multiple correlation coefficient = 0.72, determination coefficient = 0.52). It could

Table 1

item		1. frequency of message			2. message to title		3. message to concept		4. preference for sketch			5. message to final model	
student	category score	1-7	8-14	15-21	0-1	>=2	0	>=1	<=5	6-10	>=11	0	>=1
A	27	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	1
B	29.5	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	1
C	32	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	1
D	33	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	1
E	35.5	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0
F	31.5	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0
G	39.5	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0
H	30.4	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0
I	31	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	1
L	26	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0
M	33.5	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	1	0
N	31.5	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	1
O	30.5	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	1
P	27.5	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	1	0
R	35	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0
S	34.5	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0

be asserted that a fairly strong correlation was observed according to the multiple correlation coefficient.

The range score shows that the most influential item for the evaluation was #4, the number of messages to the preference page of sketches (range = 5.43), followed by #3, the number of messages to the concept page (range = 4.80). It can also be observed that planners thought it highly important how users evaluated their sketches. The advice and questions from users, in the conceptual stages, played a role in raising the quality of the planners' proposals. Naturally the outcome showed that the number of messages from to the final model and title pages had no influence on the evaluation of the proposals (Table 2).

20

Conclusion

utility of item	range	category	partial correlation coefficient
1. frequency of message	4.41	1-7	2.47
		8-14	0.29
		15-21	-1.94
2. message to title	2.76	0-1	-1.73
		>=2	1.04
3. message to concept	4.80	0	-2.40
		>=1	1.04
4. preference for sketch	5.43	<=5	-1.91
		6-10	0.28
		>=11	3.53
5. message to final model	0.30	0	-0.13
		>=1	0.17

Table 2

1. The different view points of planners (designer), specialists and users could be shared through the WWW and incorporated into the design process. This combination results in *KANSEI* oriented judgments and *KANSEI* oriented association images.
2. The author would like to name such a network environment, in which cooperative design is achieved through associated images of planners, users and other participants, "Image Associative Retrieval Design Method using WWW".
3. The attempt to respond to the question 'How can the demands of users be reflected in the design process?' has resulted in a variety of design processes, and has made us predict the existence of a parallel designing method.
4. Further, it could be said that 'the design process by planner is not a serial process, but it likens a parallel process, in which interactive messages are exchanged between planners and users'.

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*Note:

Definition of KANSEI

The terminology KANSEI has been used in many definitions. Kansei is a terminology which unifies concepts such as sensitivity, sense, sensibility, feeling, aesthetics, emotion, affection and intuition. Through a questionnaire completed by twenty nine researchers on the Evaluation of KANSEI Special Project of the University of Tsukuba, we arrived at the following ingredients of KANSEI:

1. Subjective and indescribable functions.
2. In addition to inherited nature, cognitive expression based on knowledge and experience.
3. Interaction between intuition and intellectual activity.
4. The ability of intuitive response towards distinction of objective world.
5. The image creating function of the mind.

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